

Workshop on Artificial Intelligence & Modeling for Space Biology

Supporting the Next Phase of Space Exploration and Discovery

What: Please join us for this two-day workshop which will involve the participation of researchers and leaders in AI, modeling, biology, and medicine. Expertise is sought to outline a vision on where AI and modeling ought to be developed in the next decade towards enhancing space biological knowledge discovery and supporting health for space exploration missions.

When: Thursday-Friday, June 24-25th 2021

Where: Virtual Format

Who is Organizing: Hosted by NASA Biological and Physical Sciences (BPS) Division of NASA Science Mission Directorate, Biosciences Division at Ames Research Center

Purpose of Workshop:

This NASA workshop will involve the participation of researchers and leaders in AI, modeling, biology, and medicine. Their expertise will be sought to outline a vision on where AI and modeling ought to be developed in the next decade towards enhancing space biological knowledge discovery and supporting health for space exploration missions.

Workshop will produce a White Paper for the NASEM-CBPSS and their Decadal Survey 2023-32. It also will produce a Workshop Summary & Recommendations in a peer-reviewed Journal.

Invited AI experts will help bridge the gap between technical space biology and health needs in the next decade, and the current status of our field, with all its various space data constraints, and science knowledge gaps.

Of note, this workshop will build upon the lessons, insights, and networks enabled by the May 2021 workshop on Artificial Intelligence hosted by the NASA Science Mission Directorate (SMD). The May 2021 SMD AI workshop covers all of NASA Science (Heliophysics, Earth Science, Planetary Science, Biological, Physical, Astrophysics, etc).

This June 2021 Artificial Intelligence & Modeling for Space Biology workshop will focus on capturing the best practices and vision of AI capabilities specifically towards biological and life-science related health goals.

Who is Organizing:

Hosted by NASA Biological and Physical Sciences (BPS) Division of NASA Science Mission Directorate, Biosciences Division at Ames Research Center

Workshop Organizing Team:

Sylvain Costes, Kara Martin, Aenor Sawyer, Jenna Lang, Ryan Scott, Lauren Sanders, Dan Berrios, Amina Qutub

Date: Thursday-Friday, June 24-25th 2021

Right, the space environment introduces several different hazards (distance, confinement, hostile/closed environments, radiation, and microgravity), which have numerous biological consequences and human health risks. Left, AI has been identified as a key field to be utilized towards accelerating biological knowledge discovery, imaging/microscopy, modeling/risk, and integration with various wearables and hardware systems.

(CREDIT: Right from Cell Press, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2020.10.050>;
Left top, Cell Press, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2020.108441>; Middle left, NASA Human Research Roadmap; Bottom left, CSA/NASA image with Astroskin and David Saint-Jacques; MiniPCR Machine, NASA from ISS)

Goals, Products, Format, Participants, Domain Topics

Goals of the Workshop:

- Identify AI technological needs for the next 10 years to address scientific gaps of space biology and health
- Develop strategic framework to fulfill gaps, emphasizing research consortiums, and funding mechanisms involving public and private partnerships
- Generate roadmap for AI and Modeling in space biology and health with key necessary capabilities and potential NASA campaigns

Products:

- White paper for [NASEM-CBPSS and their Decadal Survey 2023-32](#), which workshop participants are encouraged to coauthor/cosign
- Pre-arranged peer-reviewed Journal Publication Summary

Format: Virtual workshop

Length of workshop: 2 days

- Day 1 – Overview, Keynotes, Learn from AI SMEs, State of Space Biology and Health Breakout Session 1, Writing
- Day 2 – Incubation Meeting of invited AI SMEs, Report from SME's Incubation Meeting, Report from Breakout Session 1, Breakout Session 2, Report from Breakout Session 2, Writing

Participation: 90 invitees. ~70 external AI-Data-Biology SMEs (both academic & industry). ~30 NASA internal (HQ, JSC, ARC, MSFC, GRC, etc.). All those interested in attending and contributing to the workshop are welcome.

Central Domain Topics in our Workshop:

- AI and Modeling for Knowledge Discovery: 'Omics and other Space Biological Data
- AI Applications in Imaging Space Biology Research Data (including Behavioral Analysis AI Tools for Space Data)
- Precision Medicine Utilization of AI
- Data Collection through Wearables, Sensors, Monitoring Hardware Systems and Integration with AI and Modeling Power
- Space Health Risk Predictions through AI, Modeling, Network Analyses
- Spaceflight Countermeasure Predictions Utilizing AI, Modeling, and Network Analyses
- AI Applications for Microbiology and Synthetic Biology
- AI Techniques and Translational Science Across Model Organisms and Species Towards Human Health

Vision of AI and Modeling in Our Field, Suggested References

The Vision of AI and Modeling in Our Field of Space Biology:

The era of artificial intelligence (AI) has opened new possibilities for the fields of biological sciences, physical sciences, and medicine. Because AI techniques can automate scientific and analytical processes while reducing the burden of required time and resource constraints, there are high expectations for AI-enabled knowledge discoveries. In the context of space biology and the interests of NASA, the steady growth of quantitative biological data such as DNA sequencing and omics (genomics, epigenetics, proteomics, ...) is enabling AI applications for the prediction of disease risks, the identification of potential therapeutics, and the improvement of astronaut health in general. Also, the fusion of AI tools with the field of traditional biological modeling holds promise in quickening the pace of knowledge discovery. In addition, space biology ought to leverage the well-established usage of AI for image processing for knowledge extraction in diagnostic radiology, histopathology, immunohistochemistry, and cognitive-behavioral analysis from animal-based videos. AI will play a crucial role in the development of semi-autonomous health support for flight medical officers through health monitoring and integration with wearable sensors. In the near-future, assistance in medical diagnostics will be enabled by integrating state-of-the-art biotechnologies such as in situ genetic sequencing capability with health monitoring, for real-time personalized health-risk management. Lastly of note, by pushing AI technologies to their limit to address space biological and health-related challenges, myriad applications from this endeavor will be applicable on Earth and benefit terrestrial health substantially.

Suggested Background References to Understand the Field:

- [Cell Package: The Biology of Spaceflight](#)
- [Fundamental Biological Features of Spaceflight: Advancing the Field to Enable Deep-Space Exploration](#)
- [Evidence Reports from the NASA Human Research Program](#)
- [Research Methods for the Next 60 Years of Space Exploration](#)
- [FAIRness and Usability for Open-access Omics Data Systems](#)
- [NASA GeneLab: interfaces for the exploration of space omics data](#)
- [Policy Considerations for Precision Medicine in Human Spaceflight](#)
- [FDL, 2020, CRISP, Astronaut Health Technical Memo](#)
- [Integrating Spaceflight Human System Risk Research](#)
- [Knowledge Network Embedding of Transcriptomic Data from Spaceflown Mice Uncovers Signs and Symptoms Associated with Terrestrial Diseases](#)
- [From the bench to exploration medicine: NASA life sciences translational research for human exploration and habitation Missions](#)
- [Comprehensive Multi-omics Analysis Reveals Mitochondrial Stress as a Central Biological Hub for Spaceflight Impact](#)
- [FDL, 2019, Harnessing AI to support medical care in space, Technical Memo](#)
- [Considerations for Wearable Sensors to Monitor Physical Performance During Spaceflight Intravehicular Activities](#)
- [AI's role in deep space](#)

Confirmed Speakers

Dr. Sylvain Costes
Space Biosciences
Research Branch Chief (Acting)
GeneLab Project Manager
Lead of the Radiation Biophysics Laboratory
Senior Research Scientist, Code SCR
NASA Ames Research Center

Dr. Lauren Sanders
GeneLab Staff Scientist
NASA Ames Research Center

Dr. Manil Maskey
Senior Research Scientist,
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GeneLab Project Scientist
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NASA Astronaut and
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NASA Johnson Space Center

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Co-Director, UCSF Center for
Advanced 3D + Technologies

Graham Mackintosh
AI Projects Consultant
Bay Area Environmental Research Institute
NASA Advanced Supercomputer Division
NASA Ames Research Center, Code TN

Agenda Day 1: Thursday, June 24 *all times PDT*

	Session	Presenter / Panelists
7:30 – 7:50 am	Welcome Moving Space Biosciences to Knowledge-Based Platforms Overview from 2021 Space Mission Directorate AI Workshop	Sylvain Costes NASA, BPS Lauren Sanders NASA, BPS Manil Maskey NASA SMD
7:50 – 8:40 am	Keynote AI Applications in Biosciences	Mike Snyder Stanford
8:40 – 9:00 am	Break	
9:00 – 10:00 am	Keynote AI Applications in Space Biology	Kathleen Rubins NASA Astronaut
	Learn From The Expert Mini-Symposium 4 concurrent sessions	
10:00 – 10:50 am	Single-cell biology in a Software 2.0 World	David Van Valen Caltech
	Frontiers of Machine Learning	Greg Corrado Google AI
	Artificial Intelligence, Systems Biology, Brain, and Health	Amina Qutub UT San Antonio
	AI in biology is powered by open data	Casey Greene University of Colorado
10:50 – 11:10 am	Break	
	Current State of Space Biology and Health – Resources and Challenges 2 concurrent sessions	
11:10 am – 1:00 pm	Space Biology and Physical Sciences Research	Sharmila Bhattacharya NASA Space Biology Sergio Baranzini UCSF Jon Galazka NASA, BPS Adrienne Hoarfrost Rutgers University Patricia Parsons-Wingarter NASA
	Human Health and Space Medicine	Mary Van Baalen NASA Rob Reynolds Baylor Jessica Keune NASA Aenor Sawyer UCSF
1:00 – 1:30 pm	Break	
1:30 – 2:30 pm	Breakout Session 1 Key Concept Knowledge and technology gaps in Central Domain Topics	
2:30 – 2:50 pm	Break	
2:50 – 4:00 pm (Specific cohort of participants)	Breakout Session Report Writing	Organizers, moderators, and notetakers

Agenda Day 2: Friday, June 25 *all times PDT*

Session	Presenter / Panelists
7:30 – 9:00 am (Specific cohort of participants) Incubation Meeting for Specific AI-Data Science SME Attendees Identification of key needs and knowledge gaps Development of vision for Decadal Survey white paper	Moderators Amina Qutub UT San Antonio Lauren Sanders NASA, BPS
9:00 – 9:20 am	Break
9:20 – 10:40 am Incubation Panel Report and Breakout Report	Amina Qutub UT San Antonio Lauren Sanders NASA, BPS
10:40 – 11:00 am	Break
11:00 – 11:10 am Breakout Session Kickoff	Graham Mackintosh NASA
11:10 am – 12:40 pm	Breakout Session 2 Key Concept AI applications needed by space biology and health
12:40 – 1:10 pm	Break
1:10 – 1:40 pm Open Discussion	Sylvain Costes NASA, BPS
1:40 – 1:50 pm	Instructions for Writing
1:50 – 4:00 pm	Breakout Writing Rooms (Optional) Central Domain Topic focus Collation of content for Decadal Survey white paper and journal article

Participants identify areas of expertise relating to “4 Quadrants” for breakout discussions

4 Quadrants for All Participants:

To organize discussions around AI, Modeling, space biology, medicine, the workshop organizers have developed a “4 Quadrants” framework to describe participant expertise. The areas of expertise within the quadrants are not meant to be all-inclusive, but rather to provide an overview of each quadrant. The organizers recognize that there are many ways to stratify the AI, modeling, biology, and medicine communities. The “4 Quadrants” framework was designed to focus discussion, disperse expertise across domains, and maximize the precious time attendees give to participation in the workshop.

Purpose:

The “4 Quadrants” framework will aid in distributing expertise evenly throughout the breakout discussions. These breakouts will have critical input to the white paper and journal paper deliverables.

Actions:

All participants will be asked to identify one or more main areas of expertise during registration, which will be used to stratify participants into quadrants.

Before the workshop, participants are asked to give some thought to examples of successes, challenges, and how to optimize the inherently inter-disciplinary and diverse teams required to leverage AI and Modeling towards space biology discovery and health.

Biology
Medicine
Governance
Strategic Leadership

Policy
Ethics

Those identifying knowledge gaps, operational requirements to be solved/developed.

Data Curation
Data Systems
Data Archival
Bioengineering

Those collecting or preserving data to make it AI available.

AI Algorithm Design
Technique
Development
Computer Science
Statistics

Those determining best methods for AI applications.

Data Processing
Bioinformatics
Data Science

Those acting to carry out AI methodology towards spaceflight outcomes.